

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND ARTISTIC EXPRESSION IN MAN (WOMAN)

Mirzaeva Nilufar Tursunbaevna

Psychologist of Tashkent State Technical University.

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Annotation: this article focuses on the psychological processes that occur in a person: memory, imagination, thinking, abilities and, most importantly, information about consciousness, as well as changes in them. The features of the mechanism of operation of changes in the psychological process of the female sex in particular are also mentioned with some examples.

Keywords: human, personality, psychology, psychological processes, perception, attention, change, memory, fantasy, thinking, emotion, brain, mechanism.

Psychologists say that the psychological processes that occur in humans are considered to be: sensations, perception, attention, memory, fantasy, speech, thinking, emotion, office, among others. Also, the characteristics inherent in each person themselves: interest, enthusiasm, ability and talent, temperament and character, among others, are included in the sentence of psychological processes in a person. The total sum of psychological processes can also be referred to as psychological processes in one word.

Psychological processes in humans are manifested in different manifestations in the spheres of life. Nevertheless, they will be closely connected to each other.

Psychological processes are a special property of the brain and occur only in connection with the activity of the brain. The human brain is a highly externalized matter, and psychological processes are the product of this matter, its function.

While the character, worldview, inner world of the heroes of the artistic acap is depicted in a self-centered connection between nature or the socio-cultural environment, the analysis of the tools that shape the author's artistic-aesthetic thinking, the creative individual style through a system of artistic images is one of the important practical tasks faced by researchers.

Typically, women become more likely to receive frequent descriptions of memories reminiscent of events in the life of an aging capu, repeatedly speaking to those around them.

- Bul handkerchief know for me what kagap cherished masculinity-a, Oypopuk? - kethaturib appointed again in the tone of taqid Gavharshod Begim.

- Bilurmen, my queen, bilurmen! - the concubine girl nodded and made a confirmation gesture. - The BOL handkerchief Khagan will be considered the wedding gift of Our said to you!

- Not only a wedding gift... - The Concubine's answer came to the disappointment of Gavharshod Begim, and yanayam became more accurate. - Ul Paradise begimdin is a memory to me...

Oypopuk had heard a lot from Gavharshod Begim about Khoqoni said's gift, but had not seen the handkerchief itself. When Shahrukh Mirzo left this Fany world, every time the Queen

remembered her husband, she would take that scarf as well as a bot-bot ëgra, and she would say this gift with excitement about the way the prince gave it to her, and the way she delivered it to her relatives, her mother-in-law. In those moments, Gavharshod Begim seemed to turn into a young girl. The dark Cheek would glow and onnok would play a strange glow in his eyes until his face was red.

In fact, a simple handkerchief for a princess like Gavharshodbegim, the representative of a great kingdom, is myammo. However, the value of the handkerchief is increased by a thousand chandons, when she is adopted as a unique gift that inspires the delicate experiences of a woman's heart, the moments of adoration from the world of childhood, her first acquaintance with Shahruh Mirzo. At this point, the individual style of the IOC is clearly visible to oneself by showing the writer-woman's attitude towards Shahruh Mirza by describing the feelings of Gavharshodbegim, and thereby aesthetic influence on the reader. The exact detail ensures a lively and convincing output of the object being described, so the reader involuntarily feels what the hero has experienced, feelings of longing.

To find out how psychic phenomena occur, it is necessary to study its material basis – connected to the nervous system, since all psychological processes in a person are the result of the activity of the cranial and nervous systems.

No psychic process can be formed on its own, psychological processes occur only due to the influence of one or another trigger on the brain. When the onset of psychological processes is the action of the excitatory, its final result is the body's response to the excitatory. Any psychic activity consists of a reflective, reflective activity of the brain.

It is known that psychological processes and consciousness did not appear at once, but were polished and increased and improved as a result of a long historical evolution. The development of human psychological processes experiences phylogynesis and ontogynesis. The phylogynesis is that from the emergence of mankind to the present period, from generation to generation, psychological processes have been improved. Ontogynesis, on the other hand, is the growth and development of psychological processes with increasing age from the day the child was born to the end of his life.

The higher level of psychological processes inherent in a person constitutes consciousness. Consciousness is a higher, holistic form of psychological processes, the result of the socio-historical conditions of its formation in the labor activity of a person, in the process of constant communication with others (with the help of language).

What is the structure of consciousness, its important psychological definition?

Its initial definition is mind, given in its name itself. The consciousness of a person has formed from the complex of knowledge about our tevarak-the universe that surrounds us. K.Marx wrote that" the way the mind lives and that there is something for the mind is knowledge". Thus, important cognitive processes enter the structure of consciousness, with the help of which a person constantly enriches his knowledge. Among these processes, sensations and perception, memory, imagination and thinking can be added.

As a result of the direct reflection of triggers that affect the brain with the help of sensations and perception, the emotional picture of being in the mind, formed in the imagination of a person at that moment, is embodied. When memory relaxes the images of the past in the mind, imagination forms an figurative model of what is a need| object, but not in the present.

The second definition of consciousness is the expression in which a clear distinction between a subject and an object is made, that is, a person knows exactly what belongs to the concept of

"not me" with the concept of "I". A person who was the first in the history of the world of living organisms to break away from it and put himself in opposition to the environment maintains this opposition and discrepancy in his consciousness. Within living beings, his own self is capable of self-knowledge, that is, of directing psychic activity towards self-research. A person consciously evaluates his behavior and, in general, himself. The separation of "I" "From" "Not Me" is the path that everyone experiences as a child, occurring in the process of his self-awareness.

The next definition of consciousness is to ensure the purposeful activity of a person. The creation of the goals of activity is part of the function of consciousness. In this, the motives of activity arise and are squashed, volitional decisions are made, how the execution of actions goes is taken into account, appropriate adjustments are made to it, etc. In the implementation, coordination and orientation of the target-seeking activity, it is necessary to treat the occurrence of any disorder as a violation of consciousness as a consequence of the disease or for any other reason.

Finally, the fourth definition of consciousness is the inclusion of a certain attitude in its composition. The world of emotions inevitably enters the consciousness of a person. It contains complex objective and, above all, social relations in which a person is attracted by himself. In this place, as in most other cases, pathology helps to better understand the essence of normal consciousness. When suffering from certain mental disorders, the violation of consciousness is determined precisely by a violation in the area of feelings and relationships: the patient, until then, will end up not leaning on the mother he loved unconditionally, will speak with a about his loved ones, etc.

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